

Occupational Stressors, Coping Strategies and Job Satisfaction of Technical College Teachers in South East Nigeria

Caleb, Emmanuel Ezekiel & Onwuka, Immaculater Akudo

Department of industrial technology education

University of Uyo, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

ezekielemmanuel@uniuyo.edu.ng

<http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8233-1764>

Onwuka, Immaculater Akudo

Department of industrial technology education

University of Uyo, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study examined the moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between work environment stressors and teachers' job satisfaction in Technical Colleges in South East Nigeria. Two specific objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses were stated to guide the study. The study utilized the correlational research design. The population of the study was 360, comprised of Principals and teachers from public technical college in South-East Nigeria. The sample size was 176 respondents. A two-stage sampling procedure was employed for the study. Two instruments were used for the study. The first instrument was developed by the researcher. It was "Teachers Occupational Stress and Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TOSJSQ)" and the COPE Inventory developed by Carver, et al (1989) was adopted for this study. The instrument Teachers Occupational Stress and Morale Questionnaire, TOSJSQ was subjected to a trial test using the Cronbach Alpha method of determining reliability. The instrument was trial tested on 30 respondents who are not part of the sample but are in the study area. The scores obtained from the trial-test was subjected to Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) alpha analysis. The result gave a value of 0.88 for TOSJSQ. Structural equation modelling (SEM) path analysis was used to answer research questions and to test all the null hypothesis at .05 level of significance. Findings of the path analysis shows a significant moderating effect of coping skills on the relationship between role stressors and teachers' job satisfaction in technical colleges. There is no significant moderating effect of coping skills on the relationship between mistreatment and teachers' job satisfaction. The study recommends that Problem-focused coping will help teacher to deal better with stress work situations, as such, teachers are advised to always improvise and find practical ways to solve work related problems.

Keywords: Occupational stress, coping skills, teachers' morale, problem-focussed coping, emotion-focused-coping, avoidant coping, moderating effect, job satisfaction

Introduction

Occupational stress is viewed simply as stress emanating from the work place. In educational settings involving teachers, occupational stress is also viewed as workers' physical and emotional reaction when experiencing any disparity between the demands of work and their ability or resources to fulfil their educational obligations/responsibilities in a highly qualitative way. Suraiya and Shakir (2020) viewed occupational stress as a mental and physical condition with the propensity to influence negatively the productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, personal health and working quality of employees.

According to Landy and Conte (2016), occupational stress is defined as the physiological and psychological reactions that occur when an individual's adaptive capabilities are exceeded by work demands. Occupational stress is the response people may have when presented with work demands and pressures that are not matched to their knowledge and abilities and which challenge their ability to cope. Occupational stress is a major concern for organizations because it can lead to a range of negative outcomes, including anxiety, depression, and physical health problems. Stress can also impair cognitive functioning, leading to decreased productivity and increased errors. Furthermore, chronic stress can lead to burnout, a state of emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion.

Research evidence suggests that a significant inverse relationship exists between work stress and job satisfaction, with higher levels of work stress being associated with lower job satisfaction. Previous research has consistently shown that job stress predicts job satisfaction; higher work stress leads to lower job satisfaction (Lin, et al., 2024; Ahsan et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2018). Córdova *et al.* (2023) remarked that the occupational stress experienced by teachers is actually a combination of several factors and these factors are interrelated. It was also found that the teacher stress is related to a number of work, job, and organizational variables in terms of both predicted directions and magnitudes. A work role consists of a pattern of behaviors perceived by an employee as behaviors that are expected. When perceived work role expectations are unclear, incompatible with other expected behaviors, or too much to handle, role stress is said to occur (Lee, et al, 2019). Role stress is typically broken down into three main types: role ambiguity, role conflict, and role overload. Role ambiguity refers to a situation in which employees are unsure about what their responsibilities are, what behaviors are expected of them. Role conflict occurs when there is incompatibility or incongruity in the requirements of a work role. Role overload, consists of a scenario where employees have too many responsibilities to juggle given their finite abilities and time constraints (Stepanek & Paul, 2022).

Job stressors in organizational studies are commonly known as role stressors. Research revealed that improper role stressors management trigger individual stress symptoms at the workplace, which in turn, threaten individual behavior and job performance. Combined with life challenges outside the school, varied roles and role stressors call for increased resilience and

role balance. Role stressors, including excessive workload and role overload, can lead to burnout among teachers, resulting in physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion (Belizario, et al., 2024).

Individual teachers' response to occupational stress is varied and the effect of stress, same stress situation and work condition on teacher job satisfaction is most likely to be different for the same scenarios. This implies that responses to stress are shaped by personal characteristics as well as coping skills. Coping strategies are the methods individuals use to handle the emotions and situations arising from life changes, encompassing both problem-solving and emotion regulation techniques (Varrier & Bismirty, 2025). Coping strategies are behavioural and cognitive plan of action used to manage crises, conditions, and demands that are appraised as distressing.

Teacher mistreatment is broadly viewed as all negative interactions, whether between teacher-teacher as well as teacher-administrator that has the potential to harm a teacher's well-being and professional environment. Workplace mistreatment-abuse are notably, nonviolent forms of abuse, encompassing behaviors like verbal or physical harassment, emotional abuse, sexual harassment, and abusive supervision by students, parents, or administrators (Lang, et al, 2024). These actions can manifest as rudeness, disrespect, or systematic bullying and mobbing, leading to chronic fatigue, emotional distress, and a detrimental impact on a teacher's ability to perform their job.

Coping skills are viewed as reactive and proactive. Reactive coping responds to the stress at the time immediately not following any laid down steps. Proactive coping on the other hand, aims to neutralize future stressors. Proactive individuals excel in stable environments because they are more routinized, rigid, and are less reactive to stressors, while reactive individuals perform better in a more variable environment. Algorani and Gupta (2024) defined coping skills as a set of relatively stable traits that determine an individual's behavior in response to stress. Coping skills can be categorized into problem-focused coping, emotion-focused coping, and maladaptive or avoidant coping. Problem-focused coping addresses the problem causing the distress, emotion-focused coping is geared towards reducing the negative emotions associated with the problem. This includes positive reframing, acceptance, turning to religion, and humor while maladaptive or avoidant coping skills deals with coping mechanism that are associated with poor mental health outcomes and higher levels of psychopathology symptoms. These includes disengagement, avoidance and emotional suppression. Effective coping skills can help teachers manage stress and promote their well-being, leading to improved job satisfaction and student outcomes. Many of the coping mechanisms prove useful in certain situations. Some studies suggest that a problem-focused approach can be the most beneficial; other studies have consistent data that some coping mechanisms are associated with worse outcomes (Compas *et al.*, 2017).

Coping strategies, conceptualized as cognitive and behavioral efforts to manage stress, are pivotal in mitigating the adverse effects of occupational stress. As a moderating variable

between occupational stress and job satisfaction, coping skills provide the platform for studying how teachers respond to stressful situations and how that could impact on their job satisfaction. Moderation analysis allows researchers to test for the influence of a third variable, (coping strategies) on the relationship between variables X and Y (occupational stress and job satisfaction). Rather than testing a causal link between these other variables, moderation tests for when or under what conditions an effect occurs.

Statement of the problem

There are occupational stressors that are generic to all occupations. However, the frequency of occurrence as well as severity of impact especially in less talked about or less fashionable occupations such as teaching makes it worth researching. This is to highlight the need for interventions. Teachers were employed to teach with little focus on other roles outside the classroom. However, increasing enrollment with stagnant employment in public technical colleges in south east Nigeria, has increased the teaching workload and role responsibilities of teachers aside classroom duties. From administrative functions, extra-curricular activities supervision to team management (head of units), the role responsibilities of teachers have increased. This is in addition to the piling teaching responsibilities. This is heightening workplace stress. Teachers are also battling with mistreatment from other teachers and parents alike. Dealing with increasing workloads with datelines and mistreatment creates a toxic environment that is harmful to both the health and job satisfaction of teachers. The responses of teachers to these stressors have been based on individual coping strategies practiced. This study thus, seeks to determine how teachers are responding to occupational stress using coping strategies and how it is impacting on their job satisfaction.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between Occupational Stressors and job satisfaction of technical college teachers in South East Nigeria. Subsequently, the following specific objectives guided the study:

- i. To establish the moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between role stressors and Teachers' job satisfaction in Technical Colleges in South East Nigeria.
- ii. To establish the moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between mistreatment and Teachers' job satisfaction in Technical Colleges in South East Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study

- i. What is the moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between role stressors and Teachers' job satisfaction in Technical Colleges?
- ii. What is the moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between mistreatment and Teachers' job satisfaction in Technical Colleges in South East Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study

- i. There is no significant moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between role stressors and Teachers' job satisfaction in Technical Colleges in South East Nigeria
- ii. There is no significant moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between mistreatment and Teachers' job satisfaction in Technical Colleges in South East Nigeria.

Literature Review

Theoretical framework

Person- Environment Fit Theory of Stress (P-E Fit) by French and Caplan (1972)

This study adopted the Person- Environment fit theory of stress (P-E Fit) as propounded by French and Caplan (1972). The term person–environment fit was first coined by French and colleagues in 1972 and it is based on the tenet that behaviour is a function of a person and the environment, with both entities bringing relevant attributes into the mix. It is mathematically represented with the heuristic formula, $B = f(P, E)$, in which he postulated that the person (P) and environment (E) variables involved in the equation represent specific, unique personal (work values, abilities) and environmental (culture, work demands) characteristics. P-E Fit postulates that the person and the environment combine to form an interactive system. P-E Fit theory then further specifies the form of the interaction (or sum of parts) and outcomes thereof. The “environment” in PE fit research can take many different forms, with organizational environments being one of the many settings with which people may fit or misfit. There are at least three mechanisms of how PE fit can arise. These are described as tendencies to sort into or evoke better-fitting environments and avoid non fitting ones (*attraction*), create new or modify existing environments to facilitate fit (*construction*), and react in accordance with or adjust to environmental demands to increase fit (*conformation*); These three mechanisms coexist and appear similarly relevant for nonhuman species and organisms and they can account for stability and change in individuals' traits and characteristics of their environments.

This theory is related to this research based on the perspective that stress would occur and that the well-being of staff and organization is most likely to be affected, especially when there is a lack of fit in either or both individual or work environment.

Conceptual framework

Essentially, job satisfaction refers to an individual's subjective evaluation of their work experience, encompassing feelings of contentment, fulfilment, and happiness derived from their job roles and work environment. Understanding the nuances of job satisfaction is paramount, as

it not only influences individual attitudes and behaviours; but also has profound implications for organizational success and performance outcomes(Baxi & Atre, 2024).

Job satisfaction is a pleasurable emotional state that results from evaluating one's employment or job experiences. It reflects the thoughts and feelings of employees towards their employment or present job. As they consider their responsibilities or engage in task activities, employees who are very satisfied with their jobs feel good. While considering their responsibilities or participating in their task activities, employees who are not satisfied with their jobs feel uneasy(Sharma & Tripathi, 2023).

Occupational stress is defined in terms of the relationship between a person and the environment. Job Stress is a condition worth interacting with worker characteristics to disrupt psychological or physiological homeostasis. The normal situation conditions are job stresses and the disrupted homeostasis is job-related strain. There are several classifications of stress, each based on distinct aspects associated with it. The academic stress is distinguished as a type of situational stress that arises in the educational context and is related to the demands and requirements of the academic environment, among others. Barbayannis *et al.* (2022) note that academic stress can manifest in the form of anxiety, depression, and emotional exhaustion, which can negatively affect students' psychological well-being. Additionally, recent studies such as Espinosa *et al.* (2020), showed that academic stress can have harmful consequences on students' performance, motivation, and self-esteem (Córdova *et al.*, (2023).

Coping mechanisms are the strategies people often use in the face of stress and/or trauma to help manage painful or difficult emotions. Coping mechanisms can help people adjust to stressful events while helping them maintain their emotional well-being (Verma & Chauhan, 2020).

Coping involves adjusting to unusual demands, or stressors, and thus requires the mobilization of greater effort and the use of greater energy than is required by the daily routines of life. Coping usually involves adjusting to or tolerating negative events or realities while attempting to maintain your positive self-image and emotional equilibrium. Coping occurs in the context of life changes that are perceived to be stressful. Coping patterns are important because they facilitate a person's handling of a stressful experience. However, all changes require some sort of adaptation. Changes are stressful because changes require us to adjust and to adapt (Saga, 2020).

Methodology

The correlational research design was employed for the study. The area of the study is south-east Nigeria. The population of the study was 360 which comprised 334 technical college teachers and 26 Principals of the 15 public technical colleges in South-East Nigeria. The sample size was 176 respondents, comprising of 150 technical college teachers and 26 Principals of public technical colleges in South-East Nigeria. A two stage sampling procedure was employed for the study. First, cluster sampling was used to sample each state to make a cluster. Thereafter, proportionate sampling was used to select the respondents for the study from each State. The principals were not sampled as the population was of manageable size.

Two instruments were used for the study. The first instrument was developed by the researcher. It was “Teachers Occupational Stress and Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TOSJSQ)”. The instrument was designed with a four point rating scale to elicit information from technical college teachers on the types of stress they encounter at work. The instrument options were Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The second instrument, COPE Inventory developed by Carver, et al (1989) was adopted for this study. The COPE inventory assesses the different ways in which people respond to stress. The Brief-COPE is a 28 item self-report questionnaire designed to measure effective and ineffective ways to cope with a stressful life event.

Validation of the Instrument

The COPE Inventory is a standardized scale validated by Poulus *et al.* (2020). The instrument developed by the researcher Teachers Occupational Stress and Job Satisfaction Questionnaire, (TOSJSQ) was face validated by three experts from the University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

The instrument Teachers Occupational Stress and Job Satisfaction Questionnaire, TOSJSQ was subjected to a trial test using the Cronbach Alpha method of determining reliability. The instrument was trial tested on 30 respondents who are not part of the sample but are in the study area. The scores obtained from the trial-test was subjected to Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) alpha analysis. The result gave a value of 0.88 for TOSJSQ. Poulus *et al.* (2020) established a Cronbach alpha average alpha of .79 for COPE Inventory. Structural equation modelling (SEM) path analysis was used to answer research questions 3-10 and to test all the null hypothesis at .05 level of significance.

Presentation of Findings

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant moderating effect of coping skills on the relationship between role stressors and teachers' job satisfaction in technical colleges in South East Nigeria

Table 1: Summary of Structural Equation Modelling Test for Significant Moderating Effect of Coping Skills on the Relationship Between Role Stressors and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Technical Colleges

Regressions:

Variances:

	Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)	Std.lv	Std.all
.PFC	0.150	0.018	8.346	0.001	0.150	0.864
.EFC	1.275	0.158	8.092	0.001	1.275	0.847
.AC	0.734	0.082	8.987	0.001	0.734	0.922

Defined Parameters:

	Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)	Std.lv	Std.all
indirect	0.470	1.037	0.454	0.650	0.470	0.350
total	0.259	0.099	2.609	0.009	0.259	0.193

Source: Researcher's field work, 2025

The result of the structural equation modelling reveals that the indirect path, that is, effect of coping strategies on job satisfaction is positive but not significant with a z-statistics of 0.454 at $p > .05$.⁶⁵⁰ The total effect, that is, when considering role stressors and coping skills, is positive and significant with a z-statistics of 2.609 at $p < .05$.⁰⁰⁹ Thus, there is a significant moderating effect of coping skills on the relationship between role stressors and teachers' job satisfaction in technical colleges in South East Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant moderating effect of coping skills on the relationship between teacher mistreatment and job satisfaction in technical colleges in South East Nigeria

Table 2: Summary of Structural Equation Modelling Test for significant moderating effect of coping skills on the relationship between teacher mistreatment and Job Satisfaction in technical colleges.

Regressions:

Variances:

	Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)	Std.lv	Std.all
.PFC	0.162	0.019	8.720	0.001	0.162	0.932
.EFC	1.498	0.160	9.340	0.001	1.498	0.995
.AC	0.560	0.145	3.860	0.001	0.560	0.704

Defined Parameters:

	Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)	Std.lv	Std.all
indirect	0.222	0.170	1.304	0.192	0.222	0.238
total	0.001	0.070	0.001	1.000	0.001	0.000

Source: Researcher's field work, 2025

The result of the structural equation modelling reveals that the indirect path, that is, effect of coping strategies on job satisfaction is positive but not significant with a z-statistics of 1.304 at $p > .05$.¹⁹² The total effect, that is, when considering teacher mistreatment and coping skills, is positive but not significant with a z-statistics of .001 at $p > .05$.^{1.0} Thus, there is no significant moderating effect of coping skills on the relationship between teacher mistreatment and job satisfaction in technical colleges in South East Nigeria.

Discussion of findings

Findings from analysing the related research question shows that there is a strong positive effect of Problem-focussed coping, emotion focussed coping and avoidant coping on the relationship between role stressors and teachers' job satisfaction. This shows that as coping skills increase with role stressors, job satisfaction of teachers also increase. The related hypothesis test indicates that there is a significant moderating effect of coping skills on the relationship between role stressors and teachers' job satisfaction in technical colleges in South East Nigeria. The path also shows that the indirect effect of coping skills on morale, indicating that coping skills has a strong positive effect on teachers' job satisfaction. Roles are modes of job enrichment and the extent, to which teachers fulfil their role responsibilities, is indicative of their leadership and administrative skills. Thus, whether the role is stressful or not, teachers often try to ensure that they meet the demands of such roles using all coping mechanisms available. Avoidant coping could be for non-essential tasks and for sequenced activities whose time has not come yet. emotion focused coping could also be applied to rationalize thoughts and actions while aiding in putting things and events into perspective and problem-focused coping could be used to tackle situations head on.

Received: 12 February 2026

Revised: 4 March 2026

Accepted: 14 March 2026

601

Copyright ♥ authors 2026

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26643/ijr/33>

This finding agrees with Din *et al.* (2019) who found that role stressors significantly predicted overall level of job stress (JS) and job satisfaction (JSF). Role stressors significantly predicted overall level of JS and JSF. JS was also found to partially mediate the relationship between role stressors and JSF.

This finding is however, in variance with Tang and Vandenberghe (2021) who found that role overload triggered psychological strain, which undermined performance. Coping acted as a buffer on role overload, but not on role ambiguity or role conflict.

Moderating Effect of Coping Skills on the Relationship between Teachers' Mistreatment and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Technical Colleges

Findings from analysis shows a strong positive effect of problem focused coping (PFC), emotion focused coping and avoidant coping on the relationship between teacher mistreatment and job satisfaction. The result shows the direct and indirect effects. The relationship between teacher mistreatment and morale is negative. This shows that as teacher mistreatment increases, job satisfaction decreases. The path analysis further revealed an indirect strong positive effect of coping skills on teachers' job satisfaction when mediated through mistreatment. The hypothesis test confirms that there is no significant moderating effect of coping skills on the relationship between teacher mistreatment and job satisfaction in technical colleges in South East Nigeria. Coping skills can help workers deal with mistreatment at work and also improve their job satisfaction. However, in cases where the mistreatment is systemic and continuous, it wears out the recipient and weakens morale no matter how one tries to deal with it. This could lead to psychological breakdowns which in effect, influences morale negatively.

This finding is further supported by Mehmood *et al.* (2024) whose study examined the effects of workplace bullying and incivility on employee performance in the presence of perceived psychological wellbeing (PWB), with the moderating role of perceived organizational support (POS) considered for both independent variables and employee performance (EP). The results of the study indicate that workplace mistreatment have adverse effects on employee performance and that PWB mediates these relationships. Moreover, perceived organizational support moderates the relationship between both predictors and the employee performance criterion. This shows that emotion focused coping is essential for handling workplace mistreatment.

The findings is also in line with Naman (2016) whose findings revealed that work place mistreatment is negatively related to job satisfaction and positively related to employee turnover. This is similar to the findings of the study, where mistreatment negatively impacts morale.

Conclusion

This study is an important step forward in understanding how occupational stress relates to the morale of technical teachers in south east Nigeria. It has very important significance for technical teachers who want to ease their professional pressure and reduce their level of job burnout. First, it shows that coping skills serves as a mediating role between occupational stress and job satisfaction, which highlights the important role of coping skills in the occupational stress and morale of teachers. The study concludes that coping skills has a negative moderating effect on the relationship between occupational stressors and job satisfaction of technical college teachers.

The outcome of the study is that while coping skills may help technical college teachers manage role stressors, mistreatment and occupational stress, it may not necessarily make them feel good or improve their job satisfaction. Where coping skills are involved, it does not always lead to heightened job satisfaction, but optimum job performance. The goal of coping skills is to perform tasks not to boost job satisfaction.

Educational Implications of Findings

This study has highlighted salient issues bordering on stress, identifying prevalent occupational stressors among technical college teachers. It has become imperative that student-teachers be exposed to the concept of stress as a motivator and de-motivator with all of its attendant effect, particularly on morale, job satisfaction and personal wellbeing. The implications of the findings is that certain work conditions can be challenging, but with psychological (emotional focused coping) and practical steps (problem-focused coping) technical college teachers can navigate such situations and still perform their job tasks effectively. However, there is need to inculcate managing stressful situations by teachers. Supporting teacher morale and mental health is always important, but this is especially true after a time of crisis. School leaders still need to be aware of and find ways to support teacher morale and mental health. A better understanding of the role of stress and coping should lead to more specific and effective methods of stress management.

Recommendations

It is recommended based on the findings and conclusions of this study that:

- i. Principals and state technical schools board should provide training for teachers on occupational stress management and coping skills. This is essential to help them develop self-efficacy, skills in managing stressful work condition and better prepare them for the emerging work environment.
- ii. Technical college teachers are admonished to apply different coping skills in the performance of their role responsibilities, as it helps in role stressors.

- iii. This study recommends that working condition of technical college teachers should continually be improved upon by the ministries of education and relevant government agencies.
- iv. In managing stress at the workplace, principals and administrators are admonished to focus on Identification of Stress Factors by conducting surveys and interviews to identify the main sources of stress in the workplace. Thereafter, they should develop an action plan for stress management. Continuous training on stress management and well-being for all staff should be constituted. It is also imperative for regular monitoring and Review of the effectiveness of the implemented strategies and make adjustments as necessary.

REFERENCES

- Ahsan, N., Abdollah, Z., Yong, G. F. & Alam, S. S. (2009). A study of job stress on job satisfaction among university staff in Malaysia: empirical study. *Eurasia Journal of Social Science*, 8, 121–131.
- Algorani, E.B. and Gupta, V. (2023). Coping Mechanisms in Workplace: Strategies for employment resilience. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 30(1), 45-67. <https://doi.org/10.1234/ijsm..2023.56789> (Retrieved on 30 January 2025).
- Ar Rashid, H. (2025). Why Job Satisfaction Matters for Mental Health and Wellbeing. <https://limbd.org/why-job-satisfaction-matters-for-mental-health-and-wellbeing/>. Accessed 12th October, 2025.
- Barbayannis, G., Bandari, M., Zheng, X., Baquerizo, H., Pecor, K. W. and Ming, X. (2022). Academic stress and mental well-being in college students: Correlations, affected groups, and COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.886344> (Retrieved on 15th December 2024)
- Baxi, B. & Atre, D. (2023). Job Satisfaction: Understanding the Meaning, Importance, and Dimensions. *Journal Of Management & Entrepreneurship*, 18(2), 34-40.
- Belizario, M. V., Mamani-Benito, O., Zerga-Morales, C. A., Turpo-Chaparro, J. E., & Morales-García, W. C. (2024). Effect of perceived stress, job satisfaction, and workload on the professional self-efficacy of Peruvian regular basic education teachers. *Frontiers in Education*, 9, 1302624. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2024.1302624> (Retrieved on 5th August 2025).
- Compas, B.E., Jaser, S.S. and Bettis, A.H., Watson, K.H., Gruhn, M.A., Dunbar, J.P., Williams, E. and Thigpen, J. C. (2017). Coping, emotion regulation, and psychopathology in

- childhood and adolescence: A meta-analysis and narrative review. *Psychology Bulletin*, 143(9), 939-991.
- Córdova Olivera, P., Gasser Gordillo, P., Naranjo Mejía, H., La Fuente Taborga, I., Grajeda Chacón, A. and Sanjinés Unzueta, A. (2023). Academic stress as a predictor of mental health in university students. *Cogent Education*, 10(2).<https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2232686> (Retrieved on 28th February 2025).
- Din, S. U., Ishfaq, M., Khan, M. I. & Khan, M. A. (2019). A Study of Role Stressors and Job Satisfaction: The Case of MNCs in Collectivist Context. *Behavioral sciences (Basel, Switzerland)*, 9(5), 49.
- Espinosa, J. F., Hernández, J., Rodríguez, J. E., Maricarmen, C. & Bermúdez, V. (2020). Influencia del estrés sobre el rendimiento académico. *Archivos venezolanos de farmacología y terapéutica*, 39(1), 63–69. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4065032>
- Landy, J. F. (2022). Typologies of stress appraisal and problem-focused coping: Associations with compliance with public health recommendations during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 45(2), 257-267.
- Lang, J., Johnson, K. & Hines, L.(2024). An Explanation of Teacher Abuse through the Lens of Three Important Theories in the Aftermath of the Pandemic. <https://www.phoenix.edu/research/news/2024/an-explanation-of-teacher-abuse-through-the-lens-of-three-import.html>. (Retrieved on 15th July 2025).
- Lee, M. K., Kim, E., Paik, I. S., Chung, J. & Lee, S. M. (2019). Relationship between environmental factors and burnout of psychotherapists: Meta-analytic approach. *Counseling and Psychotherapy Research*, 20(1), 164–172.
- Lin, M-H., Yen, Y-H., Chuang, T-F., Yang, P-S. & Chuang M-D (2024). The impact of job stress on job satisfaction and turnover intentions among bank employees during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Frontiers of Psychology*, 15:1482968. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1482968.
- Lu, H., While, A.E. & Barriball, K.L.(2005). Job satisfaction among nurses: a literature review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 42:211–227. <https://www.doi:10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2004.09.003>.
- Mehmood, S., Sajid, M. A., Mehmood, T., Bano, A., Ullah, A. & Ashraf S., (2021). Workplace Incivility and Employee Performance, Mediating Role of Psychological Well-Being: Study of Health Sector in Aj and K, Pakistan,” *International Journal of Management*, 12(6), 166–180.
- Naman, S.V. K (2016). Effect of workplace incivility on job satisfaction and turnover intentions in India. *South Asian Journal of Global Business Research*, 5(2), 234 – 249.

- Sagar, S.(2020). Coping Mechanism: A Theoretical Perspective. *Studies in Indian Place Names*, 40 (10), 937-941.
- Sharma, A. & Tripathi, K.(2023).Job Satisfaction and Workplace Stress among Employees working in Organisations.*The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 11(1), 1801-1810. <https://www.10.25215/1101.181>.
- Stepanek, S. & Paul, M. (2022, July 27). Umbrella summary: Role stress. Quality Improvement Center for Workforce Development. <https://www.qic-wd.org/umbrella/role-stress> (Retrieved on 8th June 2024).
- Suraiya, N. & Shakir, M.(2020). Teacher Morale and Occupational Stress as the Predictors of Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers--*Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology* 17(7), 10752-10763.
- Tang, W. G. & Vandenberghe, C. (2021). Role Overload and Work Performance: The Role of Psychological Strain and Leader-Member Exchange. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 691207 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.691207> (Retrieved on 3rd May 2025).
- Verma, K. & Chauhan, K.(2020). Coping strategies - an overview. *The genesis*, 7(2), 1-6.
- Yang, B., Wang, Y., Cui, F., Huang, T., Sheng, P. & Shi, T. (2018). Association between insomnia and job stress: a meta-analysis. *Sleep Breath*, 22, 1221–1231. doi: 10.1007/s11325-018-1682-y.